

To Study the Consumer Attitude Towards Purchase Intention of Online Courses on Udemy Using Co-Relation with Reference to English Speaking and Excel Among Gen-Z in Ahmedabad

Shashwat Sharma¹, Chandni J. Vidani^{2*}

Narayana Business School Ahmedabad

Corresponding Author: Chandni J. Vidani, cleverminds.cj@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to examine the consumer attitude toward the purchase intention of online courses on Udemy among Gen-Z individuals in Ahmedabad, specifically focusing on English speaking and Excel courses. The Gen-Z population, born between the mid-1990s and early 2000s, is known for its digital savviness and preference for online learning. As online education platforms like Udemy have gained significant popularity, it becomes crucial to understand the consumer attitudes that drive their purchase intentions. The questionnaire will measure consumer attitudes towards online courses on Udemy, including factors such as Perceived utility, perceived convenience of use, course quality, and instructor trustworthiness are all factors to consider. Respondent's readiness to pay for English speaking and Excel classes will be used to determine purchase intent. Data collected from the survey will be analyzed using correlation analysis to examine the relationship between consumer attitudes and purchase intention. The findings will provide insights into the factors that influence Gen-Z's decision-making process when considering online course purchases on Udemy. The study will help us understand the significance of English speaking and Excel courses in this demographic's educational preferences. The results of this research will be beneficial for online education platforms, course creators, and marketers to enhance their offerings and marketing strategies, ultimately catering to the needs and preferences of Gen-Z learners in Ahmedabad

INTRODUCTION

Learning and development in educational support services refers to the process of enhancing the skills, knowledge, and abilities of individuals who work in the education sector, such as teachers, counselors, and administrators (Vidani, 2015). This process may involve various forms of training, professional development, coaching, and mentoring to help individuals improve their performance and effectiveness in their roles (Vidani & Solanki, 2015).

There are several key benefits of learning and development in educational support services, including:

1. **Improved teaching quality:** By providing training and professional development opportunities for teachers and other education professionals, educational support services can help improve the quality of teaching, leading to better student outcomes.
2. **Enhanced student engagement:** When teachers and other education professionals receive training and support, they are better equipped to engage students and create a positive learning environment.
3. **Increased job satisfaction:** Providing learning and development opportunities can help education professionals feel valued and supported in their roles, leading to increased job satisfaction and retention.
5. **Ongoing improvement:** By continually investing in the learning and development of education professionals, educational support services can ensure that they are up to date with the most recent research and best practices, resulting in continuous improvement in educational quality.

To support learning and development in educational support services, organizations may offer a variety of training and professional development opportunities, such as workshops, conferences, online courses, coaching and mentoring programs, and leadership development programs (Vidani, 2015). It is important to ensure that these programs are tailored to the specific needs of the individuals and the organization, and that they align with the broader goals and objectives of the education sector (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

Types of Trainings Provided By L&D

There are various skill gaps due to the short lifespan of skills and the lesser supply of talent pool. As a result, corporate leaders are developing learning opportunities to help employees grow and succeed. This is done in order to preserve the talent pool of outstanding performers (Vidani, 2016). The growth of ace training and development programs results in the creation of these opportunities. As a result, these programs give employees a diversity of abilities. (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017) They are prepared for their current job as well as any future employment chances thanks to this (Niyati & Vidani, 2016).

So, here are some of the different kinds of employee training and development programs that businesses have used to aid in their growth-

1. Basic Literacy Skills Training

School graduates lack the fundamental abilities necessary to function in the industry today (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016). Employees must have the "Workplace Literacy and Basic Skills" to function in the workplace (Pradhan,

Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016). These abilities support the workers' full involvement and engagement with the business (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016). Thus, these comprise thinking abilities, document use, computer use, numeracy, lifelong learning, and collaboration (Vidani, 2016).

Now, the lost productivity caused by a lack of basic literacy has cost multinational corporations a fortune (Sukhanandi, Tank, & Vidani, 2018). Therefore, the lack of basic literacy is not simply a problem in rich countries; it also affects businesses in less developed ones. Few employees in this field have studied through the third grade and can read (Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016).

2. Technical Training

Technical training has grown increasingly important as a result of technological breakthroughs and the adoption of new structural designs in organizations all over the world. (Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016). These training programs attempt to update and enhance workers' technical skills. (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).

Therefore, these exponential technologies have given rise to newer job categories in various industries, including: information technology, business process management, automotive, retail, textiles and apparel, banking, financial services, and insurance are all examples of industries. Some of these jobs include data architects, digital marketers, machine learning experts, web and app developers, blockchain architects, and so on.

3. Soft Skills Training

It is impossible to estimate just how much bad communication costs a company. However, studies show that the annual cost of poor communication is in the billions of dollars. Examples of poor communication include:

- *Emails with poor grammar
- *Incorrect instruction listening and reading
- *Unread documents as a result of bad design
- *Presenting false facts out of a sense of urgency
- *Careless Proofreading

Such inadequate communication inevitably results in significant losses. These lead to lower production, greater inefficiency, and company losses (Singh & Vidani, 2016). As a result, an employee's performance is more heavily influenced by their capacity for communication with both management and their coworkers (Vidani & Plaha, 2016).

As a result, some employees have excellent interpersonal skills (Solanki & Vidani, 2016). Others, however, need some training in order to improvise using these skills. Among the skills covered in this training could be improving communication skills, listening skills, and teamwork abilities (Vidani, 2016).

4. Safety Training

An organization can provide its personnel with the necessary skills and knowledge by offering safety training (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017). The purpose of this training is to empower the staff to do their duties safely. For the

personnel, a well-developed safety Program contains guidelines and procedures (Biharani & Vidani, 2018). These rules enable people to recognize risk and take the appropriate action to deal with it (Vidani, 2018).

Employers have an ethical and legal duty to teach their staff how to perform their jobs safely (Vidani, 2018). The safety of employees is a basic requirement because they are the companies' most cherished assets (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018).

Thus, safety training strives to reduce occurrences, raise awareness, and guarantee that workers remain safe, content, and productive. Increased staff productivity and satisfaction, decreased insurance costs, and future accident rates are all benefits of an efficient safety training Program (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). Companies train employees in a variety of ways for workplace safety. These cover such things as first aid, fire drills, and evacuation (Vasveliya & Vidani, 2019).

Importance of Online Training for Trainees, Organization and Trainers

Online training has grown in popularity in recent years, and for good reason. It has a number of advantages for trainees, organizations, and trainers alike. Here are some of the key reasons why online training is important:

1. **Convenience:** One of the most significant benefits of online training is that it is convenient. Trainees can access training materials at any time and from any location, allowing them to fit learning around their other commitments. This flexibility makes online training an attractive option for busy professionals who may struggle to attend traditional classroom-based training .
2. **Cost-effective:** Online training is often less expensive than traditional classroom-based training since it removes the need for traveling, venue rental, and other associated expenses. This makes it an attractive option for organizations with limited budgets.
3. **Customizable:** Online training can be customized to meet the specific needs of trainees and organizations. Trainers can create training programs that are tailored to the unique requirements of the organization, ensuring that trainees acquire the information and abilities need to do their jobs well.
4. **Interactive:** Online training could be highly interactive, with features such as quizzes, games, and simulations that engage trainees and help to reinforce learning. This can help to improve retention rates and make the training experience more enjoyable.
5. **Scalable:** Online training can be easily scaled to accommodate large numbers of trainees, making it an ideal option for organizations with geographically dispersed workforces.
6. **Data-driven:** Online training can provide valuable data on trainee performance and engagement, allowing trainers and organizations to identify areas for improvement and refine training programs accordingly.

Overall, online training is important because it offers a range of benefits for trainees, organizations, and trainers alike (Sachaniya, Vora, & Vidani, 2019). It is a flexible, cost-effective, and customizable way to deliver high-quality training

that can help organizations to achieve their business goals and improve employee performance (Vidani, 2019).

Importance of Soft Skills and Microsoft Excel in Corporate Culture

Soft skills and Microsoft Excel are both essential components of corporate culture, and they play important roles in the success of organizations (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019). Here are some of the key reasons why soft skills and Microsoft Excel are important in the corporate world:

1. **Soft skills:** Soft skills refer to a range of interpersonal skills that are essential for effective communication, collaboration, and relationship-building in the workplace. These skills include things like communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and adaptability. Soft skills are important in the corporate world because they can help employees to work more effectively with others, build strong relationships, and contribute to a positive and productive work culture.
2. **Microsoft Excel:** Microsoft Excel is a powerful tool for data analysis, visualization, and reporting. It is used by many organizations for a wide range of tasks, from tracking sales data to creating financial models. Excel is important in the corporate world because it can help employees to work more efficiently, make better decisions based on data, and communicate complex information in a clear and concise way.
3. **Integration:** The integration of soft skills and Microsoft Excel is also important in the corporate world. Employees who possess both strong soft skills and Excel skills are well-positioned to succeed in a wide range of roles, from data analysts to project managers. They can communicate complex information effectively, work collaboratively with others, and analyze data to inform decision-making.
4. **Competitive Advantage:** Organizations that prioritize the development of soft skills and Excel skills can gain a competitive advantage in the marketplace. They are able to work more efficiently, make better decisions based on data, and build strong relationships with customers and partners.

Overall, soft skills and Microsoft Excel are both essential components of corporate culture (Vidani, 2016). They are important for building strong relationships, working more efficiently, and making better decisions based on data (Vidani & Singh, 2017). Organizations that prioritize the development of these skills are in a strong position to succeed in today's rapid and competitive business climate (Vidani & Pathak, 2016).

Psychological Traits Of Gen-Z

Generation Z, commonly known as Gen-Z, is a demographic group born around the mid-1990s and the mid-2010s subsequent to the millennials. Here are a few of the personality characteristics typically linked with Generation Z:

1. **Digital natives:** Because Gen-Z is the first generation to have grown up wholly in the digital age, they are technologically savvy. They are at ease

with a variety of devices and platforms and are often quick to adopt new technology.

2. **Diversity:** In terms of color and ethnicity, as well as attitudes about gender and sexuality, Generation Z is the most varied generation yet. They are more likely to value diversity and inclusivity and are more accepting of differences in others.
3. **Socially conscious:** Gen-Z is frequently described as politically active, with a significant interest in issues such as social justice and the environment. They have a greater tendency to be politically active and to utilize the internet to advocate for causes they support.
4. **Independent:** Gen-Z tends to value independence and autonomy, with a desire to make their own choices and pursue their own goals. They are more likely to be entrepreneurial and to seek out opportunities to work for themselves rather than for traditional employers.
5. **Anxious:** Despite their confidence and independence, Gen-Z is also a generation that is prone to anxiety and stress. They have grown up in an era of economic uncertainty, political polarization, and social media pressure, and as a result, they are more likely to experience anxiety and depression than previous generations.
6. **Desire for authenticity:** Gen-Z is a generation that values authenticity and transparency, both in their personal lives and in the brands and companies that they interact with (Pathak & Vidani, 2016). They are more likely to seek out genuine connections with others and to be skeptical of advertising and marketing messages that feel insincere (Vidani & Plaha, 2017).

Overall, Gen-Z is a generation that is highly connected, socially conscious, and independent. They are digital natives who value diversity, authenticity, and autonomy, but they are also a generation that is prone to anxiety and stress (Vidani, 2020). Understanding these psychological characteristics can help educators, employers, and marketers to connect with and engage this generation effectively (Vidani, 2018).

Research Objectives

1. To understand the level of awareness of Udemy and its online courses among Gen-Z in Ahmedabad city.
2. To investigate the elements that influence the purchase intention of online courses on Udemy among Gen-Z in Ahmedabad city, with a focus on the moderating role of price.
3. To explore the relationship between consumer attitudes towards online courses on Udemy and their purchase intention among Gen-Z in Ahmedabad city.
4. To assess the level of satisfaction among Gen-Z in Ahmedabad city who have previously purchased online courses on Udemy, and the factors that contributed to their satisfaction.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. (Egbe Osazuwa 2014) It may be pointed out that if a system for online education is easily available, people will be more open to using it. Due to the

survey's broad reach, the e-learning system was evaluated based on factors such as assessed simplicity of use, perceived utility, and intention to use, and so on (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). There was no attempt to analyze students' attitudes towards e-learning based on computer anxiety or security; it will be important for future studies to identify if a significant association exists between attitude towards e-learning and these other characteristics (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022).

2. (Afzaal Ali 2011) The results back up the validity and reliability of three remote learning satisfaction variables: student-instructor interaction, teacher performance, and course rating. These dimensions can be defined as the way the material is provided, feedback and conversations with educators, the efficacy of instructors, students' educational workload and assessment criteria in the online courses, and the comfort of the means for interaction, the convenience of system functioning for the students, and the standard of content obtained by the students (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). According to the study's findings, a large proportion of pupils on this educational institution were highly pleased with the relationship between students and instructors, instructor performance, and assessment of the course (Vidani & Solanki, 2015).
3. (Galina Volkovitckaia & Yuliya Tikhonova 2020) The study was able to reveal critical variables of customer appetite for remote education based on the nature of the participants' evaluations of the advantages and efficacy of mobile learning (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). The majority of those who took part confirmed their professional achievements as well as the fulfillment of personal educational goals. Mobile learning has been regarded as an easy, comfortable, fascinating, innovative, and modern style of learning in contrast with conventional classroom lessons (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). During the mobile learning process, students demonstrated enhanced personal responsibility and self-organization, whereas practical instruction and the integration of educational material with real-world business examples significantly increased their participation and productivity (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). The majority of the attendees expressed an interest in future business courses related to their professional activity (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017).
4. (Shabnam Gurung 2021) To motivate online students, the educational setting should be visually appealing, and instructors ought to prioritize critical thinking over information (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017). Despite the obstacles of online instruction, educators are driven to learn new technologies and make the greatest use of all available resources. In the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic, it has become vital for both instructors and pupils to keep physically active and mentally well (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). The educational institution's administration should compel teachers to receive sufficient training on learning software so that they can effectively and efficiently teach and advise students (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017).
5. (Hye Jeong Kim and Ah Jeong Hong (2019) The study's findings highlight the need of offering possibilities for learners to learn and adapt e-learning tools and infrastructure in order to improve their educational experiences (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017). For academic engagement and achievement,

universities must provide training, counseling, and support to students based on their profiles, which are built by regular examination of their experiences and level of e-learning adoption (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017). Although students are digital natives and have prior experience with e-learning, universities should explore promoting the usage of online education and other innovations in both academic and extra-curricular contexts (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017). Despite being called digital natives, members of the younger generation must prepare for the combination of digital competencies with their studies (Hong & Kim, 2018).

METHODS

Research Design: The study's research design is going to be a quantitative research design, that entails the collecting of numerical data that can be statistically examined. A cross-sectional survey approach will be utilized, with data collected from a selected group of Generation Z responders in Ahmedabad at a single moment in time.

Sampling Technique: The group of respondents for the study will be chosen using a purposive sampling technique. The target demographic will be Ahmedabad's GenZ who have bought or are thinking about buying online courses from Udemy. A sampling size calculator will be used to calculate the sample size, using a level of assurance of 95% and a tolerance of error of 5%.

Data Collection: A structured questionnaire will be used to collect data. The survey will include both closed-end and Likert-scale questions. Before administration, the survey will be pretested to make sure that it is straightforward and intelligible.

Data Analysis: Statistical techniques such as correlation analysis, descriptive statistics, and regression analysis will be used to examine the acquired data. Descriptive statistics is going to be utilized to summarize the respondents' demographic features, while correlation analysis is going to be carried out to investigate the connection between consumer opinions toward distance learning programs on Udemy and the intent to buy them.

Ethical Considerations: During the research process, ethical concerns will be factored into account. Before taking part in the study, all respondents will be asked to provide informed consent. Respondent confidentiality and anonymity will be ensured throughout the research process.

Limitations: The study's weaknesses include the likelihood of sample bias, bias regarding social desire, and the inclusion of data that was self-reported. Efforts will be made to minimize these limitations by using a purposive sampling technique, ensuring respondent confidentiality and anonymity, and using pretested questionnaires.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

RESULTS

Data Analysis

Table 1. Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.938	.936	31
*Source: SPSS Software		

The alpha coefficient for the 31 variables is .938, which is greater than .70, indicating that the items have a high level of internal consistency.

Correlation Analysis

H1: There is a strong connection between Age Group and Sponsorship of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 2. Age Group - Sponsorship

Age Group	Sponsorship
Pearson Correlation	-.181*
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.027
N	150
*Source: SPSS Software	

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Pearson Correlation of Age and Sponsorship was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r=-.181$, $p<0.05$). Hence, H1 is accepted. This shows that increment in age is inversely related to the Sponsorship of online courses.

H2: There is a strong connection between Gender and Price of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 3. Gender - Price

Gender		Price
	Pearson Correlation	.163*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.046
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson correlation of Gender and Price was found to be Positive and statistically significant ($r=.163$, $p<0.05$). Hence, H2 is accepted. This shows that Gender and Price of online courses are directly related to each other.

H3: There is a strong connection between Gender and Sponsorship of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 4. Gender - Sponsorship

Gender		Sponsorship
	Pearson Correlation	-.199*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.015
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Pearson Correlation of Gender and Sponsorship was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r= -.199$, $p<0.05$). Hence, H3 is accepted. This shows that Gender and Sponsorship of online courses are directly related to each other.

H4: There is a strong connection between Gender and Money of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 5. Gender - Money

Gender		Money
	Pearson Correlation	.242**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Gender and Money was found to be Positive and statistically significant ($r = .242$, $p < 0.01$). Hence, H4 is accepted. This shows that Gender and Money of online courses are directly related to each other.

H5: There is a strong connection between Gender and Interactive Features of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 6. Gender - Interactive Features

Gender		Interactive Features
	Pearson Correlation	.195*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.017
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Gender and Interactive Features was found to be Positive and statistically significant ($r = .195$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, H5 is accepted. This shows that Gender and Interactive Features of online courses are directly related to each other.

H6: There is a strong connection between Education and Sponsorship of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 7. Education - Sponsorship

Education		Sponsorship
	Pearson Correlation	.277**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Education and Sponsorship was found to be Positive and statistically significant ($r = .277, p < 0.01$). Hence, H6 is accepted. This shows that Education and Sponsorship of online courses are directly related to each other.

H7: There is a strong connection between Education and Money of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 8. Education - Money

Education		Money
	Pearson Correlation	-.403**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Education and Money was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r = -.403, p < 0.01$). Hence, H7 is accepted. This shows that Education and Money from online courses are inversely related to each other.

H8: There is a strong connection between Education and Discounts of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 9. Education - Discounts

Education		Discounts
	Pearson Correlation	.256**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Education and Discounts was found to be Positive and statistically significant ($r = .256, p < 0.01$). Hence, H8 is accepted. This shows that Education and Discounts of online courses are directly related to each other.

H9: There is a strong connection between Education and Effectiveness of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 10. Education - Effectiveness

Education		Effectiveness
	Pearson Correlation	-.165*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.044
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Education and Effectiveness was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r = -.165$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, H9 is accepted. This shows that Education and Effectiveness of online courses are inversely related to each other.

H10: There is a strong connection between Education and Reputation of Instructor of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 11. Education - Reputation of Instructor

Education		Reputation of Instructor
	Pearson Correlation	-.215**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.008
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation between Education and the Reputation of Instructor was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r = -.215$, $p < 0.01$). Hence, H10 is accepted. This shows that Education and Reputation of Instructor of online courses are inversely related to each other.

H11: There is a strong connection between Education and Interactive Features of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 12. Education - Interactive Features

Education		Interactive Features
	Pearson Correlation	-.198*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.015
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Education and Interactive Features was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r = -.198, p < 0.05$). Hence, H11 is accepted. This shows that Education and Interactive Features of online courses are inversely related to each other.

H12: There is a strong connection between Education and Academics of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 13. Education – Academics

Education		Academics
	Pearson Correlation	-.237**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Education and Academics was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r = -.237, p < 0.01$). Hence, H12 is accepted. This shows that Education and Academics of online courses are inversely related to each other.

H13: There is a strong connection between Education and Search Engine of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 14. Education – Search Engine

Education		Search Engine
	Pearson Correlation	-.225**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.006
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Education and Search Engine was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r = -.225, p < 0.01$). Hence, H13 is accepted. This shows that Education and Search Engine of online courses are inversely related to each other.

H14: There is a strong connection between Employment Status and Sponsorship of online courses among the Gen-Z of Ahmedabad.

Table 15. Employment Status - Sponsorship

Employment Status		Sponsorship
	Pearson Correlation	-.176*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.032
	N	150
*Source: SPSS Software		

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation of Employment Status and Sponsorship was found to be Negative and statistically significant ($r = -.176$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, H14 is accepted. This shows that Employment Status and Sponsorship of online courses are inversely related to each other.

DISCUSSION

- 62% of the respondents were from '22-25' age group.
- 58% of them are males.
- 79.3% of them doing Post- Graduation
- 51.3% of them being students
- Course Content' is the most important factor for deciding to purchase an online course.
- Limited interaction with instructors' is the biggest concern when purchasing an online course
- Professional Development' is the type of Online course that most are interested to purchase.
- Social Media' is the biggest medium of finding out about Online Courses
- Around 60% respondents support the idea that Reputation of the course instructor is very significant
- Gen-Z of Ahmedabad have higher Purchase Intention to buy the online Courses which offer Greater convenience, reliability, enhancement of skill and Interactive Sessions with Instructors at an affordable price while not compromising on the Effectiveness of the Course Content and knowledge of the Instructor

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, The study's findings provide useful insights into the tastes and habits of the target consumers, notably the Ahmedabad Gen-Z population, when it comes to online courses.

The study revealed that course content is the most important factor influencing the decision to purchase an online course, indicating that individuals prioritize the quality and relevance of the material being taught. However, limited interaction with instructors emerged as the biggest concern when

considering online course purchases, suggesting that respondents value opportunities for engagement and personalized guidance.

The type of online course that generated the most interest among the respondents was professional development, indicating a desire to enhance their skills and knowledge in a specific field. Social media was identified as the primary medium for discovering information about online courses, highlighting the importance of digital platforms in reaching and engaging with the target audience.

These findings are useful for providers of courses and educational institutions attempting to meet the needs and tastes of the Gen-Z population in Ahmedabad. By focusing on delivering high-quality course content, facilitating meaningful interactions with instructors, leveraging social media platforms for marketing, and cultivating reputable instructors, course providers can better align their offerings with the expectations and desires of this specific target audience.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research is still needed on the topic of the study the consumer attitude towards purchase intention of online courses on Udemy using Co-Relation with reference to English speaking and excel among Gen-Z in Ahmedabad.

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